

Re:Crete – Reuse of concrete blocks from cast-in-place building to arch footbridge

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ABSTRACT

About 9% of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions worldwide are due to the production of cement, key constituent of concrete. Concrete also contributes to a large share of demolition waste, usually coming from building structures that are discarded because of functional obsolescence rather than of technical deficiency. Current practice for treating end-of-life concrete is to landfill it or crush it into aggregates used in new concrete mixes. Instead, a little-explored strategy consists in extending the service life of concrete elements by reusing them in new constructions. Following this paradigm, this paper presents a proof-of-concept prototype that reuses blocks cut out of obsolete cast-in-place concrete walls for a new structural application: a 10 m-long post-tensioned segmented arch footbridge. The paper details the design, material sourcing, and construction processes while highlighting the unusual features of the approach. The structural behavior is verified with a finite element analysis model and validated by load testing. A comparative life cycle assessment shows that the arch construction presents a significantly lower global warming potential than recycled concrete (−71%) or steel (−74%) alternatives and is very competitive to a timber one (+9%). In conclusion, the project proves the feasibility of a new circular economy application for the construction industry, in which new and reliable concrete structures are built with little to no cement inputs.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Concrete, currently the most ubiquitous construction material on earth, is made of sand and gravel bonded together by cement reacted with water. To produce the cement, raw materials, mainly limestone and clay, are extracted, transformed and transported, leading to significant environmental impacts [1]. The annual production of 4 gigatons of cement worldwide [2] is accountable for 9% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [3] and a high share of many other air pollutants such as nitrogen oxide, sulfur oxide and particulate matter [4]. Moreover, the limited extraction capacities of sand, gravel and limestone [5–7] combined with the increasing demand for concrete is expected to lead to a shortage of these raw materials in the near future.

On the other end of the concrete life cycle, concrete rubble constitutes approximately 30% of construction and demolition waste in Europe [8]. This rubble is usually crushed and downcycled as backfilling for excavated areas [9] or used as a sub-base for road construction. Less

often, crushed demolition concrete is recycled in new concrete mixes where it can replace up to 40% of natural aggregates. However, these recycled aggregate concrete mixes often demand higher cement amounts than conventional ones. This leads to similar levels of CO₂ emissions between recycled aggregate concrete and conventional mixes, particularly when transport distances of recycled aggregates are long [10,11].

In current contexts, the demolition of building structures most often results from their premature functional obsolescence – e.g. due to evolving spatial needs of users, urban densification, real-estate dynamics, and energy improvement plans – rather than from technical deficiency [12]. As a consequence, load-bearing components are discarded even though they are still in good condition and fully capable of serving similar load-bearing purposes over a longer period [13]. In addition to the loss of technical function and its related economic value, the premature crushing of concrete may also constitute a missed opportunity to benefit from readily available aesthetic or heritage values.

There is therefore a need to develop and promote other means to avoid new cement production, delay demolition waste generation, and

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maintain the intrinsic values of existing structural concrete components. In environmental impacts terms and according to circular economy principles, the preferred way to simultaneously address these objectives consists in avoiding or limiting new construction [14]. Besides, maintenance, renovation, transformation and strengthening of existing structures can extend their service life while satisfying new safety or comfort requirements. When preservation of an obsolete structure is not possible – i.e. due to a mismatch between new functional requirements and the functions that the structure may provide – element reuse should be preferred over demolition. Element reuse consists in (1) carefully deconstructing the structure into useful elements, and (2) recovering their functionalities by assembling them into a new structure. The process extends the service life of the elements beyond the one of their source structure, minimizes waste generation, avoids the production of new material for the target structure, and preserves most of the element intrinsic values. In contrast to recycling, which may still occur at a later stage, reuse avoids as much material reprocessing as possible. Hence, reuse also delays end-of-life greenhouse gas emissions and other adverse environmental impacts.

Deconstruction techniques have been developed to meet the needs of transformation or demolition in dense urban contexts where nuisances must be limited [15]. In the case of cast-in-place reinforced concrete structures, the extraction of structural components, notably slabs or walls, is done using mobile sawing machines. These elements can then be lifted, transported to a new construction site, and reassembled with new connections. Little-known and rarely implemented, the reuse of concrete elements from obsolete buildings in new projects is seen as a promising approach to expand the application of circular economy principles in the construction industry.

1.2. Objectives

The main goal of this work is to demonstrate through a proof-of-concept prototype named “Re:Crete”, the feasibility of reclaiming pre-existing cast-in-place concrete elements to recreate new structures. The Re:Crete footbridge prototype is a 10-m spanning post-tensioned segmented arch (Fig. 1) built with 25 concrete blocks sawn from the basement walls of a building undergoing major transformations. This prototype illustrates one technically possible method to reuse concrete elements. By proceeding with material sourcing, design and construction, the unknowns and challenges are identified and addressed. Is an appropriate stock of elements available on time and in a sufficient quantity? What margin in procurement should be taken to anticipate the risk of parts eventually being unsuitable for reuse? Can the mechanical properties of the reclaimed concrete elements be assessed with sufficient confidence? What are the techniques to extract, prepare and reassemble cast-in-place concrete elements? How can the design deal with the intrinsic geometric variability of the set of sourced elements? Is the structure made of reclaimed elements safe and reliable? What are the environmental benefits of such a construction method in terms of global warming potential? Those are questions addressed in this work.

1.3. Methodology

The questions given in Section 1.2 underline the specificities of reuse in the design process. This is illustrated by Fig. 2 and was previously identified by Gorgolewski [16]. In a standard project procedure, concept, preliminary and detail design phases follow each other. Once these design phases are completed, the properties and geometry of the structure are determined (“property and geometry definition”), the elements can be ordered (“element bill”) and the production of the elements – e.g. steel rebars, concrete formworks, cement and aggregates – can start (“material production”). This leads to the opening of the construction phase during which the new structure is built before being delivered to the user (“commissioning”).

In a reuse project procedure, the design must be able to adapt to the variabilities of the often yet unknown stock of reclaimed elements [16]. Assumptions are made on the possible stock during the concept and preliminary design phases. During or after the preliminary design phase, material sourcing is carried out to identify a stock suitable for the intended structure (“stock identification”). The final choice of a stock depends on the properties and geometry of the stock elements (“property and geometry assessment”). The detail design can then be completed, and the assumptions made during the preliminary design can be validated or corrected. Prior to construction, the chosen elements must be deconstructed from the former structure (“element deconstruction”) and prepared for the new project (“element preparation”).

The design and construction process of the Re:Crete arch follows the phases of a reuse project shown on Fig. 2 and shows the feasibility of reusing pre-existing cast-in-place concrete elements in new structures. The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the state-of-the-art technologies and research on the reuse of concrete elements, on the reuse in bridge construction and on the design and construction of segmented arch bridges. It concludes with a summary of identified research gaps. Section 3 presents the complete design and construction process of the Re:Crete arch, from conceptual design to assembly. Load-testing results and a non-destructive assessment of the prototype are detailed in Section 4. Section 4 is then completed with a comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) between the proposed reuse solution and similar constructions with other more conventional materials. The obtained results and potential future work are discussed in Section 5. Section 6 concludes the contributions of this paper.

By describing the design and construction process of the Re:Crete prototype, this paper demonstrates that well-known construction methods such as concrete sawing and post-tensioning can be applied to build a reliable structure made of reclaimed concrete elements, with only minimal input of new cement. It also highlights how such a circular approach highly influence the project process, from sourcing of the reclaimed concrete blocks to their assessment, extraction, and reassembly. Finally, this case-study proves that reusing pre-existing cast-in-place concrete elements is a convincing strategy to lower the environmental impacts of new structures.

Fig. 1. Re:Crete footbridge prototype: (a) revealing the texture of reclaimed concrete blocks and (b) holding 24 people on it.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the design phases.

2. State-of-the-art

2.1. Structural design and component reuse

Before industrialization, construction materials were commonly reused locally because it was a cost- and time-efficient strategy compared to labor-intensive new production [17]. Today, the reuse of load-bearing elements in building structures is still occurring but at a much reduced frequency [17–21]. Densley Tingley et al. [22] and Dunant et al. [23] highlighted the main barriers to the adoption of reuse in practice: supply chain dynamics, costs, limited demand, traceability and quality certification. Other authors have shown that structural assessment of reclaimed components can overcome uncertainties regarding structural capacity [17], and that implementing databases for element stocks and establishing a market is essential for the broad adoption of reuse in the construction sector [22–24].

Little research regarding the unusual process of designing structures from reused elements can be found in the literature. As illustrated on Fig. 2, conventional structural design assumes that members are fabricated according to design specifications – e.g. member cross-sections and lengths – and in unlimited quantity. Conversely, when reusing structural elements, the design is governed by stock element characteristics – e.g. cross-sections, element dimensions, and quantities [16]. Brütting et al. [25,26] showed discrete structural optimization techniques to design truss and frame structures that make the best use of a stock of reclaimed elements whilst considering typical ultimate and serviceability limit states. Their objective was the minimization of structure environmental impacts which are quantified through LCA. Similar work was carried out by Bukauskas et al. [27], Warmuth et al. [28] and Brütting et al. [29] employing fast heuristics to allow for almost real-time structural design optimization. Kim and Kim [30] employed genetic algorithms to optimize the weight, embodied carbon, and cost of frame structures made from reclaimed steel elements. Marshall et al. [31] combined genetic algorithms and bin-packing heuristics to explore the potential of designing building envelopes composed of reclaimed concrete panels.

2.2. Reuse of concrete

Although reuse of concrete is a little implemented practice, a few dozen projects reusing prefabricated concrete panels have been realized since the 1980s [32–34]. The reuse of prefabricated elements is eased by a disassembly procedure inverse to the construction sequence. The use of a limited set of different components with distinct sizes and the controlled homogeneity of the concrete quality casted in a factory also facilitates the reuse of a prefabricated construction system.

One of the earliest documented examples of prefabricated concrete panel reuse is the construction of 320 flats in the Gothenburg area (Sweden) with reclaimed panels from a mass housing building [35]. The deconstruction of the mass housing building started in 1984. Hooked connections between slabs and walls eased the separation of the panels that were then lifted using newly screwed anchors. Panels were then cleaned using high-pressure water jets prior to reconstruction. Another pioneering project is the construction of a 5-storey building in 1986 in

Middelburg (the Netherlands) that reuses slab, facade, roof and balcony elements from another prefabricated mass housing building [35,36]. The separation of elements was done using a diamond saw and facilitated by loose concrete infills at the connections.

In Germany, a dozen of low-rise buildings have been built since 1999 reusing prefabricated concrete panels from mass housing buildings [32,33]. The buildings were typically built with precast walls and prestressed concrete slabs extracted from mass housing projects built in the German Democratic Republic (GDR). While many projects tried to reuse original building parts with minimal transformation, some also employed cut parts to increase design flexibility. One prototype built with reused cut parts has also been designed to be demountable, thanks to removable heavy-dowel connections [37].

Conversely, projects reusing structurally elements reclaimed from pre-existing cast-in-place concrete structures seem inexistent to the authors' knowledge. Reclaimed cast-in-place concrete elements have been used as non-structural outdoor design elements, to create pavements [38], garden walls or outdoor furniture [39] in a downcycling process.

2.3. Reuse applied to bridge structures

2.3.1. Circularity of bridge structures

Bridges are often remarkable structures with high societal significance, allowing the crossing of various obstacles and making itineraries shorter. At the same time, the construction and maintenance of these structures require large amounts of materials [40]. Recent reviews showed that only few literature exists on circularity concepts applied to bridge design and construction [41]. Circularity implies that the material loop is closed, and that products or material lifespan is extended through repair, reuse or recycling instead of disposal. Coenen et al. [40] developed a circularity indicator that takes into account material inputs – e.g. reused or recycled material –, the adaptability and the reusability of a bridge structure. This indicator then serves as a decision-making tool between bridge design alternatives.

The following sections give an overview of reuse strategies applicable to bridge design and construction: like-for-like reuse of bridges or their components and upcycling reuse for new bridges. The environmental benefits of the strategies presented in the following review were never explicitly studied.

2.3.2. Like-for-like reuse of bridges

Like-for-like reuse implies that a deconstructed structural system or component is reused for a similar function elsewhere. In the case of bridges, the practice exists in the industry but very few examples are documented in the literature. In Poland, precast reinforced concrete I-shaped beams, in service for over 40 years, were tested to evaluate their remaining capacities and potential for reuse in a new bridge [42]. Recently, the construction company Implenja deconstructed and rebuilt a bridge on a new site in Norway [43].

The Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management of the Netherlands developed a circular bridge made of concrete components designed for disassembly and future reuse [44]. Similarly, the Striatu bridge is a prototypical footbridge showcasing a reversible assembly of 3D-printed sections [45]. In all these cases, the bridges can only be

reused for spans and loads similar to their original plan, which exemplifies well that reversibility of the connection is not a sufficient condition to achieve effective circularity.

Besides, army corps of engineers worldwide have been using dismountable structures in their operations for a long time already. The Bailey bridge, a notable example developed during World War II, consists in steel truss panels that can be reassembled together to create variable-length and -height girders [46].

2.3.3. *Upcycling reuse for new bridges*

Another strategy involving reuse consists in the recovery of components for new constructions while diverting their initial purpose. Remarkable examples of this process are the bridges built by Toni Rüttimean in Latin America and Southeast Asia [47]. Over 1000 bridges were built with and for local communities thanks to the procurement of leftover pipelines and cables that were reclaimed from old offshore oil rigs or ski lifts. Designs were also proposed, but never built, in Ireland and Denmark to reuse decommissioned wind turbine blades as footbridge girders [48,49]. The Re:Crete footbridge prototype presented in this paper falls in this category.

2.4. *Segmented arches and beams*

In segmented construction systems, the efficient combination of many smaller entities forms a larger structure. For example, a segmented arch is made of voussoirs whose length are much smaller than the span of the arch. Although traditionally built with stone blocks or masonry, the principle can be equally applied to constructions with concrete blocks. For instance, Long et al. [50] presented the construction of arch bridges using the “FlexiArch” system where precast concrete blocks are glued to a flexible membrane on their top. Due to their tapered shape, the concrete blocks form an arch when the bridge is lifted onto its site with a crane. The arch becomes stable as soon as it is restrained at the abutments. The FlexiArch bridge is then backfilled to stabilize the arch for asymmetric live loads.

Instead of backfilling, another way to connect individual blocks into a segmented structure while overcoming the low tensile capacity of natural stone or concrete is the application of post-tensioning [51]. A review of post-tensioned stone structures was presented by Boote and Lynes [52] and some notable projects are listed hereafter. A well-known example is the Padre Pio Church designed by Renzo Piano and Peter Rice with stone arches spanning up to 45 m [53]. Another recent example is The Queen’s Building in Cambridge [54]. Already in 1954, Hossdorf [55] suggested building the new “Teufelsbrücke” in Switzerland as a batter-post bridge made of post-tensioned granite. Unfortunately, this design was never built. Jürg Conzett designed two post-tensioned stone bridges in Switzerland (Fig. 3): (a) the “Punt da Suransuns” whose granite deck blocks are post-tensioned by a carrying stressed-ribbon [56], and (b) the “Wasserfallbrücke”, whose post-tensioned is applied on top of granite blocks [57]. Hennecke and Kusser [58] realized several segmented and post-tensioned granite bridges that do not show an arch shape but are straight beams. This is made possible by employing external post-tensioning cables embedded at the bottom of the beam section.

Rather than natural stone, pre-cast concrete elements with embedded centric post-tensioning cables were employed by Halding et al. [59,60] to build so-called “pearl-chain” arch bridges. U-shaped Ultra-High-Performance Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC) segments are also often connected via post-tensioning for the construction of straight beam footbridges. A first notable example is the Passerelle des Anges in France, designed by Rudy Ricciotti [61]. The Martinet footbridge, seen on Fig. 3(c) was the first of a series of UHPFRC segmented footbridges built in Switzerland [62]. The Alfred-Herrhausen footbridge is a cable-stayed bridge with a segmented tree-like pylon (Fig. 3d). The pylon segments are connected via internal post-tensioning cables [63]. This non-exhaustive list of realized projects shows the large potential of applying post-tensioning to stone or concrete segmented arches or beams to obtain high-performance structures.

Fig. 3. Segmented post-tensioned bridges: (a) Punt da Suransuns, J. Conzett, Switzerland, (b) Wasserfallbrücke, J. Conzett, Switzerland, (c) UHPFRC Martinet footbridge, Emch + Berger, Switzerland, and (d) Alfred Herrhausen bridge, schlaich bergermann partner, Germany. Image courtesy for (d): schlaich bergermann partner.

2.5. Research gaps

Building on the presented literature-review, the following research gaps are identified:

1. Design procedures used in case studies that involve structural component reuse where little described (Section 2.1);
2. The feasibility of reusing elements extracted from cast-in-place concrete structures for new structural purposes is yet to be demonstrated (Section 2.2);
3. The environmental benefits of reuse for bridges have not yet been thoroughly evaluated (Section 2.3);
4. The design of a post-tensioned segmented arch with reused concrete voussoirs has not been developed (Section 2.4).

The Re:Crete arch described in the following sections aims at answering the above questions and to provide initial concepts to fill the identified research gaps.

3. Design and construction process

3.1. Concept

The Re:Crete arch aims to make the best use of the readily-available structural quality of reclaimed concrete, namely its compressive strength. For this reason, the prototype shape is an arch, as it allows the transfer of applied loads to the supports via compression forces. The geometry of the arch is shown on Fig. 4(a). The 25 concrete blocks form a segmented circular arch with an opening angle of 26°. The arch has a span of 10 m, a rise of 1.20 m and a width of 1.20 m. The design and application of post-tensioning is inspired by the segmented construction systems presented in Section 2.4 and is explained in the following paragraphs.

An efficient way to check the stability of an arch is to draw its thrust line, i.e. a line formed by all the points of applications of the compression force resultants acting on each cross-section of the arch. The geometry of the thrust line and the force magnitudes within are easily constructed by means of a force diagram, in orange on Fig. 5, right [64]. When the thrust line lies outside the cross-section thickness, the arch is unstable [65]. Moreover, to guarantee the durability of the blocks and to avoid cracking of the concrete and penetration of external substances,

the entire cross-section should remain in compression under service loads. This is the case if the thrust line remains in the inner third (the ‘core’) of the blocks cross-section.

As illustrated on Fig. 5(a), the slenderness of the Re:Crete arch is such that it would become unstable when subject to asymmetric external loads: part of the thrust line would lie outside the core of the arch. In the case where backfill is not an option, the thrust line can be brought back within the core of the arch by installing post-tensioning cables that run through the centroids of all blocks, Fig. 4(c). The benefit of post-tensioning are well illustrated with graphic statics [66] as shown on Fig. 5(b). Due to the curvature of the arch and static equilibrium, the applied tension in the cables is balanced by an additional force on each block, normal to the arch curve (in red). The magnitude of the post-tensioning force can be tailored to ensure that on each block, the sum of self-weight force (in grey) and added normal force (in red) is significantly bigger than the applied live load resultant (in blue). As a result, a change in live load magnitude has little effect on the thrust line geometry, which remains within the central core of the blocks, and hence does not impede the stability of the arch. A related consequence is that the compression force in the blocks is significantly increased but this is unproblematic in relation to the high-compressive strength expected in the concrete blocks.

The Re:Crete arch is also equipped with two steel tie rods to take up the horizontal resultant of the thrust at the supports, Fig. 4 (a) and (d). In a real-world application the thrust is typically taken by end abutments.

3.2. Design values

The footbridge prototype is designed to resist the self-weight of the concrete blocks and a temporary live load from pedestrians. The live load is assumed to be 1.5 kN/m². No other superimposed permanent loads are considered.

The reclaimed elements are considered as existing products since their precise dimensions and properties are verified prior to construction, as explained on Fig. 2. The uncertainty of dimensional variability usually assumed when manufacturing happens after the design phase is thus avoided. Therefore, the load safety factor applied to the self-weight of the blocks at ultimate limit state (ULS) is beneficially defined using an ad-hoc probabilistic method proposed by the Swiss standard for existing structures [67]. The method allows calculating the safety factors with the standard deviation of the

Fig. 4. Re:Crete footbridge prototype: (a) elevation, (b) detail joints, (c) detail post-tensioning cables, (d) detail support.

Fig. 5. Post-tensioned segmented arch: (a) arch under self-weight and asymmetric live load, (b) arch subjected to post-tensioning. On the right side the corresponding force diagrams are shown.

Table 1
Safety factors for design load cases.

Load case	Self-weight	Symmetric live load	Asymmetric live load	Post-tensioning
ULS 1001	1.1	–	–	1.2
ULS 1002	1.1	1.5	–	1.2
ULS 1003	0.95	–	1.5	0.8
SLS 1010	1.0	1.0	–	1.0

dimension measurements and a given probability of failure. The safety factors are thus reduced from 1.35 to 1.1 when self-weight has an unfavorable effect and increased from 0.9 to 0.95 when self-weight has a favorable effect (Table 1). The load safety factor for live loads and post-tensioning remains as prescribed in the Swiss standard for new construction [68]. The deflections and vibrations of the prototype are verified for serviceability limit state (SLS), according to the requirements given in the Swiss standard for new construction [68].

As illustrated on Fig. 4(c), two single-strand post-tensioning cables, with a yield stress of 1 600 N/mm², are required to keep the arch cross-section in compression under asymmetric loading. As at this point of the design no concrete elements have been sourced yet, it was assumed that the mechanical characteristics of the reclaimed concrete would correspond to those of a standard C25/30 concrete specified in the Swiss standards for concrete construction [69]. This concrete grade has a characteristic compressive strength of 25 N/mm² and a design strength of 16.5 N/mm². As this concrete grade is expected to be commonly found in typical buildings, this is considered a conservative assumption.

3.3. Material sourcing

As illustrated on Fig. 2, material sourcing follows the preliminary design phase. For the Re:Crete project, stock identification is done in a non-systematic and opportunistic way, by contacting various demolition and concrete sawing companies that could supply concrete elements from ongoing or upcoming building demolition or transformation projects. The sought target thickness of the sourced blocks is between 18 and 22 cm. Potential source buildings are identified with the companies and the final choice is made based on geometric considerations, matching of planning, and geographical proximity to the construction site. Landfill sites and concrete recycling plants are also contacted but this option is quickly dismissed since most concrete parts arrive there in a heavily damaged state if not already roughly crushed.

The 25 concrete blocks are eventually supplied by a local concrete sawing company from a building ongoing major transformation. The

building structure is less than 10 years old and it is located approximately 60 km away from the Re:Crete arch construction site.

The extraction from the source building is done by sawing cast-in-place concrete components using diamond blades, as illustrated on Fig. 6(a). Most of the blocks are extracted from basement walls, but four blocks are also taken from the mat foundation of the same building, in orange on Fig. 6(f). The building transformation project initially already required the sawing of openings in those structural walls and mat foundation, but the sawing pattern is then adapted to fit the dimensions requested by the Re:Crete arch, i.e. 120 × 40.5 × 20 cm. While the walls have the required thickness of 20 cm, the thickness of the four blocks taken from the mat foundation is corrected from 24 to 20 cm by extra sawing steps. One block has been heavily damaged by handling during sawing and transportation. It is replaced by a block cut out of a wall from another house, in blue on Fig. 6(f).

After extraction, the blocks are transported to the sawing company premises, where the sides of the blocks are drilled to allow inserting the post-tensioning cables, as shown on Fig. 6(b) and (c). Fig. 6(d) and (e) show the final delivery and the storage of the blocks on the construction site.

3.4. Stock description

After delivery on the construction site, the blocks are visually inspected to ensure that no damage has occurred during transportation and handling, as proposed in methodologies developed for the reuse of prefabricated elements [70]. Only light damage is recorded, typically on the edges, as shown on Fig. 7(a).

The geometry of each block is measured to quantify the dimension variability of the 25 concrete elements and to ensure that dimensions are within the tolerances allowed by the design. This assessment showed that, presumably due to the manual marking procedure prior to sawing, the dimensions of the blocks vary by up to ± 20 mm, see supplementary data. This variation and the occasional damages on the faces are absorbed during assembly by varying the width of the mortar joints between the blocks, Fig. 4(b).

The position of the two drilled holes that hold the post-tensioning cables varies as well, Fig. 7(b). A maximum lateral spacing difference of 27 mm between the two holes is recorded, see Appendix A. Therefore, the alignment of the holes to allow a correct passing of the ducts and cables, without pinching or heavy kinking, is not guaranteed if the blocks are positioned randomly along the arch. For this reason, the blocks are sorted to reduce the difference in position between two adjacent blocks to a maximum of 8 mm. In addition, the diameter of the holes has been specified to tolerate such discrepancies. The drilled holes have a diameter of 38 mm, while the plastic duct around the post-tensioning cables has only a diameter of 27 mm. This 11-mm

Fig. 6. Sourcing the concrete blocks: (a) Sawing of basement walls, (b)–(c) drilling of holes for post-tensioning, (d) transport, (e) storage and (f) final source of all blocks.

Fig. 7. Stock assessment with (a) inspection of damages, (b) characterization of cut faces.

difference between their dimensions is larger than the 8 mm maximum position difference obtained after the sorted block arrangement, making the assembly feasible.

The variability of the stock is indeed an important aspect to consider when designing a structure with reused concrete elements and their connections. Tolerances of the methods and tools used to extract the elements must be considered early on and design decisions are necessary to absorb this variability. In the case of the Re:Crete arch, the use of variable-thickness mortar joints and the sorting of the blocks was sufficient to accommodate for all geometric variations.

3.5. Detail design

3.5.1. ULS verification

A finite element analysis (FEA) is conducted to validate the detail design of the structure with the commercial software SOFiSTiK [71]. The eccentricity between the post-tensioning cables and the centroid of the block cross-sections is considered in the model. As illustrated on

Fig. 8(a), the drilled hole diameter is larger than the duct and cable diameters and hence the cables lie at the bottom, creating an eccentricity. This is due to the tolerances assumed for assembly, as described in Section 3.4.

During the post-tensioning step, horizontal displacements at the supports are fixed at one end (pin support) and free at the other (roller support). Shown on Fig. 8(b), this simply supported system avoids introducing compression in the tension ties and other unwanted residual forces. The bending moment generated by the eccentric post-tensioning has a favorable effect that slightly uplifts the arch thus avoiding additional pressure on the centering.

After the post-tensioning step is completed, the structural system of the arch changes. The horizontal tension ties are fixed to take the horizontal thrust. Then the centering is removed, and live loads are applied. In the FEA, this staged construction is modeled via making use of primary load cases available in SOFiSTiK [71]. The tension ties are modeled as a spring element of equal stiffness. The equivalent static system is shown on Fig. 8(c).

Fig. 8. Detail design assumptions: (a) Reclaimed concrete blocks cross-section, dimensions in [mm], static system for (a) post-tensioning and (b) external live loads.

According to the design principles presented in Section 3.1, i.e. to preserve the arch stability and a fully compressed cross-section, the thrust line is expected to remain in the inner third of the block cross-section. This corresponds to a maximum allowable eccentricity of $200/6 = 33$ mm. The eccentricities calculated with FEA are below this value, with 18.3 mm under symmetrical loading (load case ULS 1002 in Table 1) and 31.9 mm under asymmetrical loading (load case ULS 1003 in Table 1). The resulting maximum compressive stress in the concrete is 3.1 N/mm^2 , which is well below the assumed design compressive strength of the concrete, i.e. 16.5 N/mm^2 . In addition, the analysis confirmed that shear stress at the arch ends is negligible compared to the shear strength of the concrete blocks, here considered as unreinforced.

3.5.2. SLS verifications

Deflections and vibrations are verified using the FE model for the SLS load case given in Table 1. Deflections due to post-tensioning, self-weight and external live loads occur at different phases. As described in Section 3.5.1, post-tensioning induces an uplift of the structure. Once the centering is removed, the tension ties elongate due to the thrust from the arch self-weight load and the resulting deflection decreases the arch rise. Live load is only applied at a later stage, once deflections due to post-tensioning and self-weight have taken place. As seen in Table 2, the resulting deflection due to live load is less than 1 mm, which is lower than 16.7 mm, i.e. the span over 600 proposed as a maximum value in the Swiss standard for new construction [68]. The first natural frequency of the bridge is computed as about 10 Hz, which is outside the problematic frequency range for pedestrian bridges according to the Swiss standard [68].

Table 2

Comparison of measured SLS deflections with FEA results and standard limits.

	Measured deflections Load-testing	Expected deflections FEA	Limit deflections SIA 260:2013 [68]
Half span loaded	1.1 mm	0.58 mm	16.7 mm
Full span loaded	1.2 mm	0.73 mm	16.7 mm

3.6. Assembly

The assembly of the Re:Crete arch, documented through videos [72], follows the following five steps:

1. Construction of a temporary timber centering;
2. Stacking of the blocks on the centering and simultaneously threading the post-tensioning ducts and cables through the side holes;
3. Pouring of the mortar into the joints between the blocks to ensure good contact between them;
4. Stressing of the post-tensioning cables;
5. Lowering and deconstruction of the centering.

The temporary timber braced-frame centering features two principal polygonal arches made from CNC-milled plywood panels, shown on Fig. 9(a-c). The centering can be assembled and removed in only a few steps, allowing the arch to be erected and later dismantled. The centering supports the concrete blocks during assembly and disassembly, i.e. when the structure is not self-supporting.

The concrete blocks are placed onto the centering one at a time, starting at one abutment, Fig. 9(b), and according to the planned sequence described in Section 3.4. Fig. 9(a) shows the passing of the plastic ducts and the post-tensioning cables through the side holes. Wooden spacers are placed between each block to avoid the sliding of the blocks on the centering and to keep the joints free for future filling with mortar, Fig. 9(c). Spacers have a trapezoidal shape and they are manually placed at a varying depth to control the width of each joint and maintain a correct location of all blocks on the arch despite the dimensional variability of the blocks, as discussed in Section 3.4. Local sanding of the end blocks is necessary to ensure their fitting into the steel abutments. Once all blocks are placed, a standard cement-based premix mortar is filled into the joints by hand, as shown on Fig. 9(d).

The mortar is chosen based on its compressive strength, which should be high enough to withstand the ULS compressive stress of 3.1 N/mm^2 . However, the mortar should also permit a subsequent deconstruction of the prototype, i.e. to easily crack the joints and separate the blocks. Therefore, a lime-cement mortar with a relatively low 28-days compressive strength of 15 N/mm^2 is used.

The mortar is left to harden for 14 days before applying the post-tension, allowing it the mortar to reach approximately 50% of its 28-days compressive strength. The tension-ties are released to allow the arch deformation during post-tensioning. The post-tensioning force of 168 kN per cable is introduced alternatively in each of the cables in four force steps, employing the hydraulic jack shown on Fig. 9(e). These alternative and small force steps limit the introduction of a transversal bending moment in the arch. Reversible wedge-barrel anchors are used to block the cables after post-tensioning. To allow the deconstruction of the arch and an eventual reuse of the post-tensioning cables, the ducts are not injected with mortar. After post-tensioning, the centering is safely lowered as the arch now supports its self-weight and is stable under asymmetric live-loads.

Designing the centering, the mortar joints and the post-tensioning anchors to be reversible with little to no damage to blocks and cables allows the Re:Crete footbridge to be deconstructed following a reversed sequence and reassembled in another location.

4. Assessment

4.1. Load testing

To validate results from the FEA (Section 3.5) with the actual structural behavior of the prototype, an experimental load test is carried out. This test is done prior to the complete disassembly of the centering, which is in the meantime simply lowered by about 3 cm, as seen on Fig. 10(b), but kept in place as a security measure. The centering also serves as a fixed point to attach the measurement gauges used to record

Fig. 9. Prototype assembly: (a)-(b) placement of concrete blocks, (c)-(d) filling the joints with mortar, (e) post-tensioning while (f) the steel bar anchor is released.

Fig. 10. Load test: (a) preparation, (b) deflection measurements, arch loaded without the centering for (c) half-span and (d) full span.

the deflections of the arch at various steps of the loading. Fig. 10(a) shows the 15 kg sandbags used to create the area load.

The load test is performed in two steps. First, the load is applied asymmetrically. As shown on Fig. 10(c), sandbags are placed on half the span. This load case represents the critical load distribution for such a structure. Second, the arch is loaded symmetrically over its full length, Fig. 10(d), reaching a total load of 1.8 tons corresponding to the design live-load of 1.5 kN/m².

Deflection measurements are compared with FEA results and maximum values allowed by Swiss standards for new construction [68], Table 2. The actual structure is less stiff than the FEA model and the measured deflections are thus larger than the calculated ones.

Nevertheless, the deflections are well under the allowed SLS limits.

4.2. Non-destructive assessments

Non-destructive assessments are conducted to validate the mechanical properties of the concrete assumed in the design. The compressive strength of the concrete blocks is estimated using a Schmidt rebound hammer [73] shown on Fig. 11(a). The position and concrete cover over the existing passive reinforcement bars are measured via a Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) [74]. The measuring process is shown on Fig. 11(b) and (c).

Rebound hammer measurements are done 24 times on 2 different

Fig. 11. Non-destructive assessments:(a) Schmidt rebound hammer, (b) and (c) GPR, and (d) GPR map of the concrete cover thickness.

blocks each. These measurements give an estimated characteristic compressive strength of the concrete equal to 23 MPa, which corresponds to the concrete strength category used in the design. GPR measurements show that the average rebar spacing in the blocks is 15 cm and that the concrete cover is between 3 and 4 cm. On Fig. 11(d), the concrete cover mapping is given. Sides of the blocs are not covered by the measurements due to the size of the instrument. Although passive reinforcement is not necessary for structural reasons, corrosion of the steel bars would affect the durability of the concrete blocks when the bridge is placed in an outdoor location. This information is thus useful to plan protective interventions prior to a future use of the arch.

As shown on Fig. 11, the assessment of the Re:Crete arch is carried out after the arch construction and serves as a validation of the design. However, material property and geometry assessment should typically

be carried out prior to detailed design and extraction of the elements from the source building.

4.3. Life cycle assessment

4.3.1. Design alternatives

Often used to compare construction alternatives, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a well-known approach for assessing the environmental impacts of comparable products [75]. Regarding load-bearing component reuse, LCA has been applied among others by Yeung et al. [76] and Küpfer et al. [77] to assess the environmental impacts of steel component reuse. In their works, alternatives including reused elements were compared with reference alternatives typical for current practice and employing newly-manufactured elements with or without recycled

Fig. 12. Elevations and cross-sections of the four alternatives, respectively: (a) recycled-concrete block arch; (b) recycled-concrete monolithic arch; (c) steel arch; (d) timber arch. Cross-section dimensions are in cm.

content. In this work, the Re:Crete arch is compared with four design alternatives (Fig. 12): (a) a post-tensioned segmented arch built using 25 recycled-concrete blocks; (b) a monolithic recycled-concrete arch with passive steel reinforcement, (c) a steel arch, and (d) a timber arch. All alternatives are designed to meet the same loading requirements and overall dimensions as the Re:Crete arch.

4.3.2. Functional unit and system boundaries

In an LCA, the functional unit quantifies the service or product provided by the studied system. In the present comparison, the functional unit is the construction and assembly of the load-bearing system of an arch footbridge. The comparison does not include non-structural elements such as railings or overlays. Additionally, abutments are excluded as they are assumed to be identical for all alternatives. However, protection from water damage of the load-bearing elements is included when relevant: water-repellent coating on the cut-sides of the Re:Crete arch and anti-corrosion paint on the steel structure of alternative (c). For (a) and (b), a new wooden formwork for pouring concrete has been considered in addition to a timber centering equivalent to the one used for the Re:Crete arch. A breakdown of material quantities in all alternatives is given in the supplementary data.

As shown on Fig. 13, system boundaries include all processes related to the obsolete-structure demolition or selective deconstruction, reusable component preparation, new resource extraction, material production, transportation, and construction work. However, the arch footbridge use, maintenance, and end-of-life stages are excluded since including them would add more uncertainty and require an in-depth sensitivity analysis that is out of scope for this paper.

A cut-off approach [78,79] is chosen to allocate impacts of recycled and reused materials. In this allocation approach, also known as “recycled-content approach”, impacts due to recycling or reuse activities are attributed to the product using the materials that result from these processes. Conversely, products that release materials for recycling or reuse are not responsible for impacts associated with these activities.

On-site measurements – e.g. electricity consumption – and the Swiss LCA database KBOB [80] are the main sources for calculating process impacts, completed with other open datasets from Switzerland [81] and Germany [82]. Average transport distances are set based on the density of material suppliers in the region for elements that are not used in the

Re:Crete arch and for which transport is not already aggregated in a process in the database. Transport distance for recycled concrete, new rebars and glulam is rounded to 30 km. For comparison, reused concrete blocks have been transported a total of 100 km from deconstruction site to assembly site.

As the construction industry must rapidly decrease its impact on global warming, global-warming potential (GWP) is used as the environmental-impact indicator to compare the alternatives. The GWP quantifies the heat absorbed in the atmosphere by greenhouse gases emitted by the processes included in the system boundary of an alternative. GWP is expressed in kilograms of equivalent carbon dioxide (kgCO_{2eq}). All quantities and GWP factors used for this LCA are detailed in Appendix A.

For alternatives made of recycled concrete, calculations are carried out assuming 40% of recycled aggregates and 60% of natural aggregates, using the GWP factor provided in the dataset developed by KBOB and the City of Zürich [81]. However, calculations would be approximately equivalent if only natural aggregates are employed. Indeed, GWP factors due to producing a same volume of new or recycled concrete are almost identical [10,11].

4.3.3. Results

The computed GWP related to the Re:Crete arch and the four design alternatives is presented in the bar chart on Fig. 14. The construction of the Re:Crete arch implies a 71%-, 63%- and 74%- smaller GWP than for the recycled-concrete block arch, the recycled-concrete monolithic arch and the steel-beam arch, respectively. GWP of the Re:Crete arch and the timber-beam alternative are in similar ranges, but the score of the timber arch remains 9% lower.

For the Re:Crete arch, the largest share of GWP is due to the transportation of the reused blocks (red) and the timber centering (yellow), each responsible for 34% of the total GWP. Mortar and post-tensioning cable production each account for 17% and 9%, respectively. GWP due to concrete sawing is negligible.

Transport distances between deconstruction and assembly sites strongly influences the environmental footprint as the transport of the 25 reused blocks emits about 1 kgCO_{2eq} per kilometer. A further reduction of transport distances would make the Re:Crete arch an even more competitive alternative to timber. For comparison, lowering the

Fig. 13. System boundaries of the life cycle assessment (dotted frame). Red arrows indicate flows of reusable elements. Black arrows indicate flows for new, recycled, or landfilled materials. Circled Ts indicate transport stages.

Fig. 14. Comparison of GWP between the Re:Crete arch and the four design alternatives.

transport distance of reused concrete blocks from 100 km to 75 km would result in the Re:Crete arch and the timber arch having an equivalent GWP. On the opposite, transporting reclaimed concrete blocks beyond 620 km would result in the Re:Crete arch having a higher GWP than the monolithic recycled-concrete arch.

Additionally, the construction of the Re:Crete arch diverted 6 tons of good-quality concrete from conventional end-of-life processes such as crushing and landfilling.

5. Discussion and future work

This work demonstrates the feasibility of reclaiming concrete elements from obsolete cast-in-place concrete buildings and reusing them for load-bearing purposes in an arch footbridge. The project fills the four research gaps identified in Section 2.5.

In response to research gap 1 on the lack of design procedures involving structural component reuse, this work provides a full description while highlighting the following challenges: 1) the inherent limited material availability and the thus necessary coordination between deconstruction and reconstruction projects (Section 3.3); and 2) the reliable application of assessment methods for reclaimed concrete components (Section 4.2). The following improvements could be made regarding each of both challenges:

1. For the Re:Crete arch project, the sourcing of the concrete blocks is handled in an opportunistic way by contacting local demolition companies (Section 3.3). This process could be carried out in a more systematic way if a detailed database of ongoing deconstruction work is openly available. It would allow minimizing transportation distance, and thus GWP, of the reclaimed elements while ensuring a good match with expected geometric and mechanical properties.
2. As opposed to what is done for the Re:Crete arch project, geometric and mechanical properties could be evaluated already on the deconstruction site, prior to extracting the elements. Non-destructive methods, such as the Schmidt rebound hammer and GPR measurements presented in Section 4.2, are reliable solutions to identify these properties. In the case of the Re:Crete arch, general conditions of the source concrete walls, and in particular their age and exposure,

suggested that they are in good condition, which was subsequently confirmed.

In response to research gap 2, the construction of the Re:Crete arch demonstrates the feasibility of reusing elements extracted from cast-in-place concrete structures for new structural purposes. The paper shows that reclaiming concrete blocks and assembling them into an arch shape with post-tensioning showcases a reliable structural behavior.

In response to research gap 3 on the environmental benefits of reuse for bridges, Section 4.3 presents the GWP evaluation of the Re:Crete footbridge. Results suggest that reusing concrete blocks significantly reduces the GWP of footbridges otherwise made of new concrete, recycled concrete, or steel. The Re:Crete footbridge GWP is also competitive to a similar design made of timber, while diverting a large amount of concrete from landfilling. Nevertheless, GWP could be reduced further by optimizing 1) transport distance of reclaimed concrete elements and 2) materials used for the temporary centering.

In response to research gap 4, Sections 3.1, 3.5, and 4.1 respectively conceptualize, detail, and test the design of a post-tensioned segmented arch with elements from a reclaimed stock and with varying dimensions. The variability of the element dimensions largely depends on the deconstruction method. In the case of the Re:Crete arch, this variability is significant but taken care of by a correct sorting of the blocks and connection details allowing some variation. The authors believe that such variation might lead to critical construction issues if it is not anticipated during the design process. Deconstruction tolerances could be reduced by using dimension gauges and stencils to calibrate the elements prior to sawing or drilling.

In a next step, the Re:Crete arch will be installed outdoor and used by pedestrians to cross a narrow river. This will allow to identify and address durability issues coming from the concrete reuse. The outdoor exposition of concrete blocks that were not initially designed for this use, requires constructive solutions to protect the structure from water and the resulting problems – e.g. rebar corrosion and freeze–thaw damages. A first simple solution is the application of a water-repellent coating on all exposed concrete surfaces. A waterproofing layer should also be placed on the top surface of the bridge to protect the joints from any water penetration. These solutions are easy to implement. However, they require regular inspections and maintenance to be effective. In

addition, prestressing ducts should be injected with mortar to avoid contact of the cables with air and water. A downside of this last measure is that it makes the deconstruction of the arch for a future reuse difficult.

For the Re:Crete arch, relatively small concrete blocks are reclaimed from building walls and are reused in a structural system where they are under pure compression. Pre-existing reinforcement bars in the reclaimed blocks are ignored. Future work will explore the possibilities to take advantage of these reinforcement bars. It will be investigated whether these bars can be reliably considered in the design of a structure, thus opening the design space of concrete reuse to structures that also resist in bending.

6. Conclusions

This paper introduces the reuse of pre-existing cast-in-place concrete as a convincing strategy to lower the environmental impacts of new structures. Building on a vast state-of-the-art review on reuse and segmented footbridges, the Re:Crete arch is designed, assembled, and tested. It is a 10-m long post-tensioned footbridge structure whose blocks are cut from walls and mats of a building under transformation. The paper highlights how the specificities of such a circular approach highly influence the design process, from sourcing of the reclaimed concrete blocks to their assessment, extraction, and reassembly. A comparative LCA shows that the construction of the Re:Crete arch is responsible for at least 63% less GWP (in $\text{kgCO}_{2\text{eq}}$) than other conventional alternatives made of recycled concrete and steel and 9% more GWP than one in timber. Moreover, the reuse of 6 tons of concrete delays inert waste disposal and avoids new raw material production. Combining well-established techniques – i.e. concrete sawing, post-tensioning, and non-destructive mechanical assessment –, this proof-of-concept prototype opens the way to new circular structural design processes. It also pioneers constructive solutions that perform as well as concrete, but without casting any of it.

Author contributions

JB initiated the Re:Crete arch project and led the structural design of the prototype with help of JD and MBM. MBM organized the material procurement and funding. All authors participated in the construction. MBM and CF oversaw public dissemination of the project. MBM is currently planning the permanent installation of the arch. CK computed the LCA with the help of JD. JD led the writing of this paper, supported by MBM. All authors actively contributed to the writing of the paper and approved the final version.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2022.07.012>.

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